

PRODUCT-FORM SOLUTION OF A QUEUEING INVENTORY WITH TWO MODES OF PRODUCTION

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Abstract: *The system under consideration is a queueing inventory system, where customers come following a Poisson process with rate λ , and inventory items are served according to an exponential distribution with parameter μ . Production of items commences when the inventory level falls below a specified threshold s , and it continues until the inventory level reaches the maximum capacity S . The time for producing one item follows an exponential distribution with a parameter β . When the inventory level further decreases to a level of r , the production rate increases to $\theta\beta$, where $\theta > 1$. The system returns to normal production mode whenever the inventory level reaches $r+1$ through accelerated production. When the system lacks inventory, it blocks customers in order to reduce holding costs. We study the system in detail and calculate the stationary probabilities. Multiple performance measures are identified. Numerical illustrations determine the optimal triplet (r, s, S) . A parameter sensitivity analysis is performed.*

Keywords: *Inventory, Production Inventory, Normal Mode of Production, Accelerated Mode of Production, Product form solution I.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Queueing theory and inventory control are central in supply chain research. In production-inventory models, items are produced internally, unlike classical queueing-inventory models where they are sourced externally. Production begins once stock hits a lower threshold and halts at the maximum level.

The production-inventory model with positive service time was introduced by Krishnamoorthy and Viswanath (Krishnamoorthy and Viswanath, 2013), and extended under the (s, S) policy by Krishnamoorthy et al. (Krishnamoorthy, Nair, and Narayanan, 2013). Otten et al. (Otten et al., 2015) studied a two-tier supplier-inventory system, while Rafiei et al. (Rafiei et al., 2015) addressed wood remanufacturing under uncertainty. Ghiami and Williams (Ghiami and Williams, 2015) analyzed deterioration in a manufacturer-buyer setup, and Sivashankari and Panayappan (Sivashankari and Panayappan, 2015) modeled variable production for deteriorating items. Further, Patra (Patra, 2018) examined imperfect production; Huang et al. (Huang et al., 2018) proposed a Stackelberg model for food supply chains; Ruidas et al. (Ruidas et al., 2019) studied demand reduction from substitutes; Karim and Nakade (Karim and Nakade, 2019) analyzed random disruptions; Liu et al. (Liu et al., 2020) and He et al. (He et al., 2022) investigated co-production; Ruidas et al. (Ruidas et al., 2023) considered high-tech products; and Dey et al. (Dey et al., 2024) developed a periodic review model for perishables. This paper analyzes a production-inventory queueing model with positive service time and an emergency production mode triggered below a critical threshold, extending Rof and Jacob (Rof and Jacob, 2024), who assumed negligible service time. Our contributions include product-form solutions, bounds for cycle time distributions, and optimization of the (r, s, S) policy. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the model, Section 3 analyzes production cycles, Section 4 formulates the optimization problem, and Section 5 gives numerical illustrations.

Notations Used:

- $\exp(\mu)$: Exponential Distribution with parameter μ
- $E_k(\mu)$: Erlang Distribution with parameter μ of order k
- $GE_k(\lambda, \mu)$: Generalized Erlang of order k with parameters λ and μ
- CTMC: Continuous Time Markov Chain

$$+g(r)[\mu_1^r/(\mu_1 - \theta)^2\theta^{r-1}(\mu_1^r - \theta^r - \theta r(\mu_1 - \theta)) + \mu_1(\mu_1^r - \theta^r)/\theta^r(\mu_1 - \theta)].$$

3.1. Stability Condition

Theorem 2. The system is stable if and only if $\lambda < \mu$.

Proof. The system is stable if and only if $\phi A_0 e < \phi A_2 e$ which implies, $\lambda < \mu$.

4. SYSTEM STATE PROBABILITY; PRODUCT-FORM SOLUTION

To find the state probability vector of $\{(I(t), C(t)): t \geq 0\}$, we consider a production-inventory system with negligible service time and no backlog. The state space is $\{(i, j): 0 \leq i \leq S, j \in \{0, 1, 2\}\}$. From steady-state analysis, the probability vector is $\pi = (\pi_0, \pi_1, \dots, \pi_S)$, where $\pi_i = (\pi_i(0), \pi_i(1), \pi_i(2))$.

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1 &= \lambda/\beta, \quad u(s) = (\lambda_1/\lambda_1 - 1)(\lambda_1^{s-s+1} + \lambda_1^{s-s} + \lambda_1^{s-s-1} - 2\lambda_1 + 1), \\ v(r) &= 1/\theta [u(s)\lambda_1^{s-r} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1 - \lambda_1^{s-s} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1 \cdot \lambda_1^{s-r-1} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1], \\ w(r, s) &= \lambda_1^{s-s} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1 \cdot \lambda_1^{s-r-2} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1, \quad l(r, s) = (\lambda_1 \lambda_1^{s-r-1} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1)((\lambda_1 + \theta)^{r-2} - \theta^{r-2}), \\ z(i) &= \lambda_1((\lambda_1 + \theta)^{r-i-1} - \theta^{r-i-1}). \end{aligned}$$

Solving $\pi A = 0$ and $\pi e = 1$, we obtain

$$\pi_i(j) = \begin{cases} \pi_S(0), & s+1 \leq i \leq S, j=0, \\ [u(s)\lambda_1^{s-i} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1 - \lambda_1^{s-s} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1 \lambda_1^{s-i-1} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1]\pi_S(0), & r+1 \leq i \leq s-2, j=1, \\ u(s)\pi_S(0), & i=s-1, j=1, \\ \lambda_1 \lambda_1^{s-i-1} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1 \pi_S(0), & s \leq i \leq S-1, j=1, \\ v(r)\pi_S(0), & i=r, j=2, \\ 1/\theta^{r-i} [v(r)\lambda_1^{r-i+1} - \theta^{r-i+1}/\lambda_1 - \theta - z(i)u(s)\lambda_1^{s-r-1} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1 + z(i)w(r, s)]\pi_S(0), & 1 \leq i \leq r, j=2, \\ \lambda_1/\theta^{r-i} [v(r)\lambda_1^r - \theta^r/\lambda_1 - \theta - l(r, s)u(s) + l(r, s)\lambda_1^{s-s-1} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1]\pi_S(0), & i=0, j=2. \end{cases}$$

Normalization gives

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_S(0)^{-1} &= S - s + u(s)[\lambda_1^2(\lambda_1^{s-r-2} - 1)/(\lambda_1 - 1)^2 - s - r - 2/\lambda_1 - 1 \\ &\quad - \lambda_1^{s-r-1} - 1/\lambda_1 - 1((\lambda_1 + \theta)^r - \theta^r)/(\lambda_1 + \theta)\theta^{r-1} - r\lambda_1/\theta] \\ &\quad - \lambda_1/(\lambda_1 - 1)^3 (\lambda_1^{s-s} - 1)[\lambda_1^{s-r-2} - 1 - (\lambda_1 - 1)(s - r - 2)] + \lambda_1/(\lambda_1 - 1)^2 [\lambda_1(\lambda_1^{s-s} - 1) - (S - s)(\lambda_1 - 1)] \\ &\quad + v(r)[\lambda_1^r/(\lambda_1 - \theta)^2\theta^{r-1}(\lambda_1^r - \theta^r - \theta r(\lambda_1 - \theta)) + \lambda_1(\lambda_1^r - \theta^r)/\theta^r(\lambda_1 - \theta)]. \end{aligned}$$

Using the component probability vector π , the steady-state vector of $\{(N(t), I(t), C(t)): t \geq 0\}$ is derived. Let $x = (x_0, x_1, \dots)$ with $x_i = (x_i(0), x_i(1), \dots, x_i(S))$, $i \geq 1$. The balance equations are

$$x_0 B_1 + x_1 A_2 = 0, \quad x_i A_0 + x_{i+1} A_1 + x_{i+2} A_2 = 0, \quad i \geq 0,$$

with

$$x_0 = \zeta \pi, \quad x_i = \zeta (\lambda/\mu)^i \pi, \quad i \geq 1,$$

for some constant ζ .

Theorem 3. If $\rho = \lambda/\mu < 1$, then the steady-state vector is

$$x_0 = (1 - \rho)\pi, \quad x_i = \rho^i (1 - \rho)\pi, \quad i \geq 1,$$

where π is the steady-state vector of $\{(I(t), C(t)): t \geq 0\}$.

4.1. Performance Measures

- Average Number of Customers in the System: $L_S = \lambda/\mu - \lambda$.
- Average Number of Customers in the Queue: $L_q = \lambda^2/\mu(\mu - \lambda)$.
- Expected Number of Inventory in the System: $E_{inv} = \sum_{j=1}^S j \pi_j = \sum_{j=1}^r j \pi(j, 2) + \sum_{j=r+1}^S j \pi(j, 1) + \sum_{j=s+1}^S j \pi(j, 0)$.
- Expected Rate of Production: $ERP = \sum_{j=0}^r \pi(j, 2)\theta\beta + \sum_{j=r+1}^{s-1} \pi(j, 1)\beta$.
- Expected Number of Customers Lost: $E_{loss} = \lambda/\theta\beta$.
- Expected Rate at which Production is Switched Off: $E_{off} = \sum_{j=s+1}^S \pi(j, 0) = (S - s)\pi(S, 0)$.
- Expected Rate of Production in Normal Mode: $ERP_{norm} = (\sum_{j=r+1}^{s-1} \pi(j, 1))\beta$.
- Expected Rate of Production in Accelerated Mode: $ERP_{acc} = \sum_{j=0}^r \pi(j, 2)\theta\beta$.

- Expected Rate at which Normal Production is Switched On: $E_{normON} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} x_i (s+1,0)\mu = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (1-\rho)\rho^i \pi(S,0)\mu = \rho\mu\pi(S,0) = \lambda\pi(S,0)$.
- Expected Rate at which Accelerated Production is Switched On: $E_{accON} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} x_i (r+1,1)\mu = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (1-\rho)\rho^i \pi(r+1,1)\mu = \rho\mu\pi(r+1,1) = \lambda\pi(r+1,1)$.

5. BOUND FOR THE PRODUCTION CYCLE DISTRIBUTION

The production cycle is the time between two successive visits to level s . Exact cycle time distribution is intractable, but a greatest lower bound (GLB) can be obtained. Consider an epoch when inventory drops to s from $s+1$ with production off. Production starts and continues until level S , switching off at time T_1 .

We compute the distribution in two cases:

i) **No customer waiting when level drops to s :** Production begins after an exponential(β) delay and continues until $S-s$ items are produced. The duration is Erlang($S-s, \beta$), denoted $E_{S-s}(\beta)$. The probability of no arrivals during this period is

$$\Pr\{E_{S-s}(\beta) < E_1(\lambda)\} = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\beta t} \beta^{S-s} t^{S-s-1}}{(S-s-1)!} e^{-\lambda t} dt.$$

ii) **One or more customers waiting at s :** Here, we compute the probability of no service completion before production ends:

$$\Pr\{E_{S-s}(\beta) < E_1(\mu)\} = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\beta t} \beta^{S-s} t^{S-s-1}}{(S-s-1)!} e^{-\mu t} dt.$$

Combining these two cases yields the probability distribution of the cycle time.

$$\begin{aligned} f(t) &= x_0 e \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\beta t} \beta^{S-s} t^{S-s-1}}{(S-s-1)!} e^{-\lambda t} dt + (1-x_0 e) \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\beta t} \beta^{S-s} t^{S-s-1}}{(S-s-1)!} e^{-\mu t} dt \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\beta t} \beta^{S-s} t^{S-s-1}}{(S-s-1)!} [x_0 e e^{-\lambda t} + (1-x_0 e) e^{-\mu t}] dt \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\beta t} \beta^{S-s} t^{S-s-1}}{(S-s-1)!} [(1-\rho) e^{-\lambda t} + \rho e^{-\mu t}] dt \end{aligned}$$

6. OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

Based on the performance measures discussed above, we construct the following cost function:

$$C(r, s, S) = E_{inv}H_c + E_{loss}L_c + ERP_{normal}N_c + ERP_{acc}A_c + E_{normON}N_{on} + E_{accON}A_{on}$$

Let H_c be the holding cost per unit, L_c the cost of lost customers, N_c the normal production cost per unit time, and A_c the accelerated production cost. The fixed costs for starting normal and accelerated production are N_{on} and A_{on} , respectively. Substituting the performance measures, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} C(r, s, S) &= H_c \sum_{j=1}^S j\pi_j + L_c \frac{\lambda}{\theta\beta} + N_c \sum_{j=r+1}^{S-1} \pi(j, 1)\beta \\ &\quad + A_c \sum_{j=0}^r \pi(j, 2)\theta\beta + N_{on}\lambda\pi(S, 0) + A_{on}\lambda\pi(r+1, 1) \end{aligned}$$

Since the expression is complex, verifying convexity is difficult; hence, we determine the optimal values numerically.

7. NUMERICAL ILLUSTRATION

For numerical analysis, parameter values are set under the stability condition. We study the effect of varying one parameter at a time on performance measures and identify the optimal triplet (r, s, S) minimizing system cost. The cost function is evaluated for different r, s, S values, with results shown in tables and (s, S) graphs for varying r . We find the optimal triplet (r^*, s^*, S^*) such that $C(r^*, s^*, S^*) = \min C(r, s, S)$. From Table 4 to Table 7, the optimal triplet is $C(r^*, s^*, S^*) = (1, 7, 11)$ with a minimum cost of \$3830.1.

Figure 1: Comparison of $C(r, s, S)$ values and line graphs for $r = 1, 2$

Figure 2: Comparison of $C(r, s, S)$ values and line graphs for $r = 3, 4$

CONCLUSION

In this article, we discuss a queueing inventory model with an alternative mode of production. Normally, production begins when the inventory level reaches s and continues until it reaches S . The production time is exponentially distributed with parameter β , and shifts to a faster mode when the inventory level falls to r , with a rate $\theta\beta$ ($\theta > 1$). Customer arrivals follow a Poisson process with rate λ , and service is exponential with rate μ . The chapter provides a product-form solution for the system state probabilities and discusses performance measures, including the least upper bound for cycle time duration and a cost function. Numerical studies are performed to find the optimal cost, and the convex nature of the cost function is verified. Future work could involve exploring more general distributions for the model's parameters.

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